

Olfactory reference disorder – empirical insights to a new ICD 11 diagnosis

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Olfactory reference syndrome
Questionnaire
Prevalence
Factor structure

ABSTRACT

Olfactory reference disorder (ORD) is defined as a persistent preoccupation with the belief of emitting an offensive body odour, even though no actual odour is present. The ICD-11 has newly introduced olfactory reference to the catalogue of mental disorders, however, standardized assessment tools allowing further research on this diagnosis are scarce. The objective of this study was to test the ORD screening tool (ORD-ST), a questionnaire we developed based on the ICD-11 criteria. The ORD-ST, as well as questionnaires on mental health and questionnaires and tests on olfaction were completed by a sample of 279 participants. The ORD-ST identified three underlying factors: conviction of possessing a perceivable body odor, checking and modification of body odor, and social impairment, together explaining 38.6 % of the variance. Retest-reliability over the course of one week was high to acceptable for the social impairment and checking subscales, and low for the conviction subscale. ORD symptoms positively related to anxiety, depression, and somatic symptoms, but not to olfactory sensitivity and olfactory attitudes. Based on those findings, we generated the hypothesis for an aetiological model of the olfactory reference disorder, in which the transition from temporary to stable beliefs of emitting a perceivable (and offensive) odor marks the crucial transition.

1. Introduction

With the release of the 11th version of the international classification of diseases (ICD-11), the World Health Organization implemented a new diagnosis of mental disease: the olfactory reference disorder (ORD). This disorder, categorized under the umbrella of obsessive-compulsive disorders, is defined by a “persistent preoccupation with the belief that one is emitting a perceived foul or offensive body odour or breath that is either not or only slightly perceivable by others” (World Health Organization, 2022). A similar definition is given by the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders in its revised, fifth edition (American Psychiatric Association and Association, 2013).

The olfactory reference disorder is quite an interesting phenomenon: While some somatic disorders are characterized by an aversive body odour, such as diabetes or typhoid fever (Liddell, 1976; Shirasu and Touhara, 2011) or even simple inflammation (Olsson et al., 2014), in olfactory reference disorder, patients do not suffer from an objective repulsive odour. Rather, they are concerned that their smell will be perceived as such by others. Hence, the ICD-11 definition states that “individuals experience excessive self-consciousness about the

perceived odour, often with ideas of reference (i.e., the conviction that people are taking notice, judging, or talking about the odour)” (World Health Organization, 2022).

In this respect, the definition resembles symptoms of the social anxiety disorder, where patients do not primarily suffer from actual social incompetence or insufficiency, but rather from their belief that others perceive them this way (World Health Organization, 2022). In fact, there are several similarities between social anxiety and olfactory reference (Reuter et al., 2024a; Tada, 2023; Tsuruta et al., 2017). Both phenomena entail a presumed evaluation of oneself by others and are characterised by a pronounced sense of inadequacy, which often carries an embarrassing or shameful quality (Swee et al., 2021). In addition, patients with olfactory reference disorder exhibit repetitive and excessive behaviours typical of the obsessive-compulsive disorder spectrum: In response to their concern about emitting an aversive body odor, they frequently check their body for odor sources, seek reassurance on their body odor by others, or try to mask or change their body odor by usage of perfume or deodorant. Ultimately, patients may even avoid social situations altogether (World Health Organization, 2022). Finally, according to the ICD definition, the described symptoms must be

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2025.116615>

Received 17 December 2024; Received in revised form 25 June 2025; Accepted 27 June 2025

Available online 30 June 2025

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“sufficiently severe to result in significant distress or significant impairment in personal, family, social, educational, occupational or other important areas of functioning.” (World Health Organization, 2022).

The implementation of this new disorder - which was previously called olfactory reference syndrome- warrants standardized assessment tools for a better understanding of this disease. Such an assessment tool is not only needed to determine comorbidity with other mental diseases, but also to clarify the prevalence of the disorder.

Previous research on olfactory reference syndrome, or “jiko-shu-kyofu”, as it is called in Asian cultures (Suzuki et al., 2004), was mainly based on case studies (Begum and McKenna, 2011; Luckhaus et al., 2003; Phillips and Menard, 2011; Prazeres et al., 2010; Pryse-Phillips, 1971; Suzuki et al., 2004) with limitations in terms of generalisability. This is also reflected in the review articles (Feusner et al., 2010; Lochner and Stein, 2003; Schmidt et al., 2019; Soman and Nair, 2023; Thomas et al., 2015). For instance, Soman and Nair (2023) write that the prevalence of the olfactory reference syndrome is estimated at 0.5-2.1 %, a statement also reported in Lochner and Stein (2003) and Thomas et al. (2015). This estimate tracks back to the review by Feusner et al. (2010), citing three studies. One of them refers to a collection of 9 patients in a psychological treatment unit, who spontaneously reported olfactory reference symptoms (Marks and Mishan, 1988), one to a case study including three patients (Forte, 1952), and the other to a – not further discussed – article written in Japanese about a survey study conducted in university studies (Kasahara and Kenji, 1971). Undisputedly, multiple case studies show the existence of olfactory reference. The most comprehensive collection reports 84 cases (Begum and McKenna, 2011), including the cases of (Pryse-Phillips, 1971), with whom’s description the term “olfactory reference” was introduced. Those informative case studies paved the way towards the ICD-11 diagnosis, which now allows for a standardized operationalisation of ORD.

The few empirical studies on olfactory reference rely on internet-based survey data. One of them uses the Yale-Brown Obsessive Compulsive Scale Modified for ORS (ORS-YBOCS; Zhou et al., 2018) in a Chinese sample of young university students. The other one used the Olfactory Reference Disorder Questionnaire (ORDQ) in a German student sample (Reuter et al., 2024b). The latter questionnaire by Reuters et al is the – to the best of our knowledge – only survey assessing the core ICD-11 features. It consists of 16 items with the answer options not at all (0) to extremely (4) and applies a time criterion of 3 months. Its clear advantages are the brevity and severity assessment, a disadvantage of the conducted study may be, that the first 4 items serve as a screening that terminated the rest of the questionnaire for 210 of the 225 participants. This clinically pragmatic and time-consuming approach does however hinder insight on how common other core features of ORD (such as conviction about possessing an unpleasant smell) are distributed in the population.

The aim of our study was the development and testing of an ORD screening tool (ORD-ST), which reliably allows for a self-assessment of symptoms related to olfactory reference in healthy and diseased population. In addition, we aimed to determine potential influencing factors of ORD. It is not yet clear, why some individuals become persistently preoccupied with their body odour. We assume several factors. From the perspective of olfactory research, an obvious assumption is that quantitative olfactory disorders, i.e., reduced olfactory function, may contribute to insecurity about the own body odour. Indeed, patients with congenital anosmia report more social insecurity than healthy controls (Croy et al., 2012). A second intuitive factor is disgust sensitivity, a trait that correlates with obsessive compulsive symptoms (Tolin et al., 2006) and was found to be enhanced in individuals with ORD (Schmidt and Grochowski, 2019). In specific, we assume that disgust to body odours (as opposed to certain foods for instance) may relate to ORD. Thirdly, in alignment with the observation that all case studies were collected in the context of psychological or psychiatric units, we posit that ORD is comorbid with other symptoms of mental disorders. Specifically, we

assume that internalising disorders (Kotov et al., 2017), which are characterised by an increased perception of insufficiency, are linked to the perception of the own body odour as inappropriate. Accordingly, we hypothesize a correlation between ORD and depression and anxiety symptoms.

To further elucidate the olfactory reference disorder, we transferred the ICD-11 criteria into a questionnaire, which we presented in an in-person study to 279 participants. We tested re-test reliability with a subsample of the participants and - in line with the content similarity of some of the ICD-11 criteria, we tested for a factorial substructure of the ORD-ST. Furthermore, we hypothesized a positive coherence of the ORD-ST with olfactory sensitivity, body odour disgust, anxiety and depression.

2. Methods

2.1. Participants

We surveyed a total of 279 individuals aged 18-63 (M = 25.6±9.0 years; 188 women, 85 men, 6 individuals indicated neither male nor female sex). Inclusion criteria for the mainly student sample were age >18, self-assessed good health and good knowledge of the German language. For the total sample, we tested whether ORD relates to olfactory function, smell behavior, depression and anxiety. For 63 participants (aged 18-60 years, M = 25.6±9.3 years, 46 women, 16 men, 1 other), we additionally tested the retest reliability after an interval of seven days. The study was part of a larger investigation on body odour which is not published yet (<https://smellodi.eu/>) and participants filled out the questionnaires and conducted the olfactory tests in a quiet room while bridging waiting time. The retest was conducted with those participants who were investigated multiple times during the larger investigation. The study was approved by the local ethical board (FSV22/016).

2.2. Material

We developed the ORD-ST by translating the ICD-11 criteria into 16 brief self-report statements. The response format is binary (yes/no), following the coding logic applied in the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-5 (First, 2014). As outlined in the introduction, another study from this year also published an ORD questionnaire, called ORDQ (Reuter et al., 2024b), that directly builds on the ICD-11 criteria. Different to ours, the ORDQ implements screening items, Likert answer format and – deviating from the ICD 11 – a time criterion concerning the past three months. As our study was conducted before publication of the Reuters study, we were unfortunately not aware of the ORDQ and hence did not compare both questionnaires.

In addition to the ORD-ST, participants reported on their mental health using the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-D; Gräfe et al., 2004; Kroenke et al., 2010), with the modules PHQ-9 for depression, PHQ-15 for somatisation and GAD-7 for anxiety. Furthermore, body odour disgust was investigated using the Body Odour Disgust Scale (BODS; Liuzza et al., 2016) and we asked for the subjective importance of olfaction (Croy et al., 2010) and smell behaviour (Perl et al., 2020). The latter questionnaire asks for the frequency of sniffing the body odour of others (partner, stranger, child) and the own (armpits, hands, ...) and, thus, directly relates to the symptom of body odour checking.

Before entering the study, n = 152 participants (including all retest participants) were tested for their olfactory performance. This was done using an ultra-short version of the Sniffin sticks screening test (Kobal et al., 1996). In that test, the examiner presents three felt-tip pens loaded with odours (banana, cinnamon, fish) to the participants, who were asked to identify the correct one in a force-choice format. If all three odours were identified correctly, participants were considered as normosmic, i.e., have a normally functioning sense of smell. If one or more errors occurred, the full 16 sticks identification test was carried out. If

less than 12 odours were identified correctly, additionally, the discrimination and odour threshold test battery were used.

2.3. Statistical methods

The factor structure of the ORD-ST was tested by principal component analysis (PCA) with varimax rotation implemented in JASP (version 18.3). The resulting factors were used to form subscales for further exploratory analyses in addition to the ORD-ST sum score. The frequency of fulfilling each ORD criterion, as well as the distribution of the sum score and the factors are provided. The stability of the ORD-ST was tested for the sum score and for the resulting ORD-ST factors using test-retest-correlation.

As the ORD-ST mean scale and the subscales violated the normality assumption (Shapiro-Wilk, each scale $p < 0.001$), we tested the relation between ORD and objective and subjective olfactory sensitivity, and all questionnaire data by calculating Spearman correlation coefficients.

Furthermore, we explored the relation of the ORD-ST to socio-demographic variables that were surveyed in the larger investigation: age and body mass index (BMI) were tested with Spearman correlation analysis, sex (male, female), occurrence of a (recovered) COVID-19 infection in the last six months (yes, no) with Mann-Witney U test; and diet (vegan, vegetarian, meat consumption) were tested with multivariate analysis of covariance (MANCOVA).

3. Results

3.1. Factor structure

The 16 items of the ORD-ST related to three underlying factors ($\chi^2=243.6$, $p < 0.001$), that explained a variance of 38.6 %. The component loading of the items indicated three subscales, which we named according to their covered content as follows: 1) “social impairment” (21.0 % explained variance) including nine items with very high loadings on this factor, 2) “checking and modification of the body odor” (8.8 %) with four items, and 3) “conviction of possessing a perceivable body odor” (8.4 % explained variance) with three items. The between scale correlations were significant (each $p < 0.001$) and low to moderate (social-checking: $r=0.328$; social-belief: $r=0.337$; checking-belief: $r=0.231$). See Table 1 for details.

3.2. Frequency and reliability

None of the tested 279 individuals answered “yes” to all 16 statements and the median of positive answers to the ORD-ST items was rather low with 18 %. This differed substantially between scales. Items for the subscale *checking and modification of the body odour* were reported frequently with a median of 50 % positive answers and a large spread of answers (see Fig. 1). This high prevalence was mainly driven by 85.7 % agreeing to try to change body odour emissions with deodorants (Table 1). Items related to the subscale *conviction of possessing a perceivable body odour* had a median of 33 % positive answers with an even larger variety of answers (see Fig. 2 and Table 1). Individual item analysis shows that half of the individuals believe to emit a strong and persistent body odour of sweat and that an equal number believe that others perceive and judge their odor. However, only 17.6 % think that their body odor is actually unpleasant.

The *social impairment* subscale– which includes most items – had a median of zero positive answers and a low variety. Item number 13 and 16, which ask for illness insight, were positively answered by 5.7 % or 4.4 % of the participants. Especially low was the percentage of positive answers to a central ICD-11 criterion for mental disorders: Only 3.2 % of individuals agreed to feel significant impairment in important areas of functioning. Those reported a mean of 8.2 other ORD symptoms, while the participants without significant impairment in functioning reported a mean of only 3.3 other ORD symptoms. We exploratorily tested the

Table 1

Questionnaire structure and percentage of positive answers. Note: the full questionnaire is provided ready to use in the supplement.

	Item	Component loading			Uniqueness	% pos. answers
		PC1	PC2	PC3		
Social impairment						
	ord15	0.703	-0.032	0.072	0.499	3.2
	<i>Does worrying about your body odor affect your personal, family, social, educational, professional or any other important area of your life?</i>					
	ord03	0.653	-0.054	0.051	0.568	4.5
	<i>Do you assume that when someone opens a window, it is because of your body odor or breath?</i>					
	ord14	0.635	0.136	0.084	0.571	6.5
	<i>Do you think that your body odor disturbs or offends others?</i>					
	ord09	0.566	0.168	0.242	0.593	9.3
	<i>Will you be sitting or standing particularly far away from other people so that they cannot detect your body odor or breath?</i>					
	ord10	0.496	0.365	-0.454	0.415	8.6
	<i>Do you change your clothes several times a day because you are afraid of smelling unpleasant?</i>					
	ord08	0.460	0.061	0.073	0.779	12.2
	<i>Do you avoid social situations in which your body odor could be noticed?</i>					
	ord16	0.459	0.017	0.421	0.612	5.7
	<i>Do you think your beliefs and behaviours about your body odor are inappropriate or exaggerated?</i>					
	ord13	0.387	0.264	0.036	0.779	4.4
	<i>Have you ever been told in the past that your preoccupation with your own body odor or breath is exaggerated?</i>					

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Item	Component loading	Uniqueness			% pos. answers	
		PC1	PC2	PC3		
Have you ever been kept from leaving your home because of your body odor or breath?	ord05	0.263	-0.028	0.131	0.913	5.7
Checking and modification of the body odor						
Do you often seek confirmation from other people that you do not smell unpleasant or offensive?	ord04	0.400	0.420	0.078	0.658	19.0
Do you try to change or avoid your body odor (e. g., with deodorant)?	ord07	-0.211	0.581	0.273	0.543	85.7
Do you repeatedly check your body odor or breath several times a day?	ord06	0.114	0.707	0.184	0.454	42.7
Do you feel the need to shower several times a day or wash your hands thoroughly?	ord11	0.042	0.641	-0.276	0.511	22.9
Conviction of possessing a perceivable body odor						
Are you convinced that certain parts of your body emit a strong and persistent odor of sweat, such as your feet or armpits?	ord12	0.210	0.259	0.321	0.786	50.9
Are you convinced that others perceive, judge or talk about your body odor?	ord02	0.155	0.142	0.608	0.586	51.3
Do you perceive your own body odor or breath as unpleasant or offensive?	ord01	0.139	-0.004	0.648	0.561	17.6

relation to other items and found that most items of the checking and modification subscale as well as of the conviction subscale were not indicative for impaired functioning, while those of the social impairment subscale were (see Fig. 2).

Test-retest reliability for the total score was acceptable ($r = 0.775$). For the subscales, the retest-reliability was acceptable to high for social impairment ($r = 0.841$) and acceptable for checking and modification of the body odor ($r = 0.627$). However, it was very low for the conviction of possessing a perceivable body odor ($r = 0.326$).

Fig. 1. Frequency of “ORD questionnaire” total and its subscales in a primarily student population of 279 individuals (thereof 88 men). Box plots with medium, quartile and range are superimposed by individual data (dots). The median is displayed below the scales, the mean and standard deviations are as follows: Total: 0.22 ± 0.15 ; social impairment: 0.07 ± 0.13 ; checking and modification of the body odor: 0.43 ± 0.26 ; Conviction of possessing a perceivable body odour 0.40 ± 0.31 .

Fig. 2. Impaired function in relation to other ORD symptoms. The overall frequency of “yes” to impaired function was at 3.2 %. Each dot presents one item of the three subscales and its relation to impaired function. The size of the dots represents the frequency of positive answers per item. Positive answers to items of the “checking and modification” subscale (pink) and “conviction” subscale (blue) were rather frequent (compare table), but not indicative for impaired function, while positive answers on “social impairment” (red) were less frequent but had a higher predictive value.

3.3. Relation to olfaction, mental health, and sociodemographic variables,

Neither objective nor subjective olfactory sensitivity related to ORD, with all correlation values being below 0.1. The subjective importance of olfaction was also not related to ORD ($r = 0.094$).

Mean smell behaviours positively related to mean ORD, indicating the people who report to consciously sniff body odours more often also report higher OSD symptoms ($r = 0.276$, $p = 0.010$). This relation was reflected in the positive correlation between self-sniffing behaviour and ORD beliefs ($r = 0.251$, $p = 0.019$), while other subscale correlations showed the same trend without reaching the level of significance. Body odor disgust did not relate to ORD ($r = -0.075$), neither for the overall, nor for the own or other disgust (each $r < 0.1$).

There was a positive relation between symptoms of mental disorders and ORD. Total ORD correlated strongest to anxiety ($r = 0.410$, $p < 0.001$), followed by depression ($r = 0.372$, $p < 0.0019$) and somatic symptoms ($r = 0.314$, $p < 0.001$). The correlations were also significant for all three ORD subscales. All correlation values are displayed in the Supplementary Table 2.

For the socio-demographic variables, men reported slightly higher

values than women in the ORD-ST mean scale and in each of the subscales, however, this difference was only significant for the social subscale ($W=6790$, $p=0.017$, $r=0.15$). Older individuals reported significantly lower overall values ($r=-0.163$, $p=0.006$), which was based on significantly reduced reports on the conviction of possessing a perceivable body odor ($r=-0.205$, $p<0.001$). However, as the majority of our participants were young, this needs to be treated with caution.

BMI was not related to ORD ($r=0.069$) and neither was diet ($F(2,274)=0.598$, $p=0.55$). The 166 participants who reported to have had COVID-19 did also not differ from the 111 who reported to not have had COVID-19, except for the social subscale with slightly lower values in the COVID experienced ($W=10347$, $p=0.037$, $r=0.123$).

4. Discussion

Our results show that ICD-11 criteria-based construction of the ORD-ST relates to three factors, which explain 38.9 % of the total variance and differ in prevalence and retest-reliability. While the overall score had an acceptable retest-reliability, it was rather high for the scale which was least often positively answered, namely social impairment, and low for the scale which showed the highest variance, namely the conviction of possessing a perceivable (unpleasant) body odor. Furthermore, we confirmed the assumed positive relation to mental disorders, but none of the other assumed relations. The results are discussed in more detail below.

The perception and checking of the own body odour are part of natural human behaviour (Perl et al., 2020). In our study, almost half of the participants reported to regularly check the own body odour or breath over the day and more than 80 % of the participants stated that they alter or avoid emissions of their body odour, e.g., using deodorant. However, while it is common to notice and evaluate body smells from time to time, our study suggests that less than 20 % perceive it as unpleasant and hardly any participants seemed to experience significant impairments from it. Thus – and in line with the diagnosis of the olfactory reference disorder – social impairment caused by the own body odour seems to be rather an exception than the norm.

A total of 3.2 % participants fulfil the criterion of significant impairment in important areas of functioning and those report substantially more ORD symptoms, especially in the area of social impairment, as compared to the other participants. This is in line with other studies using similar questionnaire based methods reporting prevalence of 2.4 %-5.5 % (Reuter et al., 2024b; Zhou et al., 2018). While our study may be more objective than those internet surveys, due to its in-person assessment, it suffers from the same problem of low generalisability. As have the other two, we investigated a primarily student sample. Furthermore, with around 300 participants our study is still small considering the previously suggested low prevalence of the disorder. In order to obtain robust data on prevalences in the whole population, large-scale approaches with a sample representative of different age groups, gender, socioeconomic status, etc. would be necessary.

Looking at the retest reliability, our results suggest that the mean ORD-ST score and the two subscales *checking and modification* as well as *social impairment* were rather stable over the course of seven days. In contrast, the perception of the own body odour as being unpleasant was not. On the one hand, this instability may be attributed to the fact that this scale contains only three items, which inherently affects its reliability. On the other hand, it also reflects the fact, that human body odours are subject to change of states such as mood, nutrition, inflammation etc. (de Groot et al., 2017) and shows that the conviction is rather a state than a trait variable.

The ORD-ST score related to smell behaviour, which is expected as such behaviour is included in the criteria of the olfactory reference disorder. Reflecting the generally high comorbidity within symptoms of mental disorders (Wittchen et al., 2003), ORD symptoms were moreover moderately correlated to all investigated mental health domains, i.e., with depressive symptoms, anxiety and somatic symptoms. This extends

previous reports on comorbidity of ORD symptoms in psychiatric in-patients (Phillips & Menard, 2011; Prazeres et al., 2010) to less severe stages of mental impairment.

In addition, we explored the association of ORD with several socio-demographic variables. Concerning gender, symptoms seem to be present in men and women. Some authors have previously reported a slight overrepresentation of women (Phillips & Menard, 2011; Reuter et al., 2024b), likely due to sample composition, while others observed more male cases (Begum & McKenna, 2011; Greenberg et al., 2016) or no gender differences (Zhou et al., 2018). In our study, we found slightly higher ORD-ST scores in males, however, the differences were small and only significant in the scale of social impairment. Thus, our results contribute to the mixed picture and point rather towards random occurrence of gender effects rather than systematic differences.

Concerning age, a slight tendency of lower ORD symptoms was found in older individuals – perhaps reflecting the general decrease of olfactory function with age (Oleszkiewicz et al., 2019). However, as mentioned above, our sample was predominantly young and is thus not suitable for a proper comparison of age groups.

Besides this, none of the other investigated variables on olfaction, physical health and diet related to ORD. The lack of relation to olfactory performance is in line with a previous study (Schmidt et al., 2021). Anyhow, this observation must be treated with caution. The reason is that we investigated a sample of young, healthy and highly educated individuals. A recent study which focussed specifically on individuals with high ORD symptom load for instance found a positive relation to disgust sensitivity (Schmidt & Grochowski, 2019), while we did not observe a relation to self- or other body odor disgust. We can also not generalize to individuals who are for instance severely obese, have a very limited diet or are hyposmic. Another interesting aspect may be in testing parosmia, a disorder leading to qualitatively distorted olfactory perception, or phantosmia, which is characterized by the perception of odorants in the absence of any odour source. Both disorders may be associated with ORD symptoms, but no research until today has investigated this relationship. Taken together, these observations lead us to generate the hypothesis for a potential model that can be applied to understand the development of the olfactory reference disorder: It is a normal human experience to perceive body odour and believe it is perceivable by others. The conviction that the own odor is unpleasant is subject to fluctuations, which is likely a normal reflection of an accurate self-evaluation shared objectively by others. Problems arise, when this conviction becomes a stable belief that others are repelled by the body odour. Facilitating mechanisms may be social insecurity and shame, which also underlie social anxiety disorders, or the presence of other mental disorders which enhance general mental vulnerability. This model could be tested in a longitudinal design. Thereby, researchers may especially focus on the hen-egg problem of whether olfactory reference disorder leads to other mental impairments or vice versa.

There are other limitations of our study. The most prominent one is the lack of a gold standard of ORD. The ORDQ could be a very good questionnaire for convergent validity. A standardized interview is currently lacking. Secondly, our sample is too small and with including only students, too biased to allow generalization over the whole population, it may just serve as a starting point for generating hypotheses for further research. Related to this, our hypothesized model needs to be tested in a longitudinal design.

5. Conclusion

In summary, our study suggests that the new ICD-11 diagnosis of ORD can be operationalised effectively in a survey format, and it may contain three different aspects: commonly held beliefs about having an unpleasant odour, frequent checking behaviours, and the less common social characteristics that occur together with general functional impairments in important areas of life.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Iiona Croy: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Julia Überschar:** Project administration, Data curation. **Antonie Louise Bierling:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Project administration, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

None of the authors report any conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

None of the authors report any conflict of interest. The work was funded by the EU project “Smart Electronic Olfaction for Body Odor Diagnostics” (SMELLODI, Grant No. 101046369).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.psychres.2025.116615](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2025.116615).

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